

A nanohybrid for photodynamic therapy and fluorescence imaging tracking without therapy

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ABSTRACT: Theranostic upconversion nanoparticles (UCNPs) are ideal candidates for personalised medicine. We present a smart, easy-to-prepare nanohybrid (NH) suitable for NIR-theragnosis and imaging tracking without triggering therapy simultaneously. The photophysical features of each component have been carefully selected in order to maximize the capabilities for theragnosis, in particular, the upconversion emission and the photosensitizer absorption. In addition, NH presents a fluorescent marker with one-photon absorption in the green and two-photon absorption cross-section at NIR wavelengths where the UCNP does not absorb, thus enabling innocuous tracking. Thus, the NH consists of NaYF₄: Yb, Er, Tm (UC_{YbErTm}) emitting in the UV, Vis and NIR; a broadband-absorbing natural porphyrin (PP) in the UV-to-NIR range but from 580 to 675 nm; and a 1,8-naphthalimide (NI) with two absorption bands, (UV, VIS), and dual emission. In vitro assays demonstrate that UC_{YbErTm}@PP/NI NH is non-cytotoxic and extremely effective for NIR-induced cancer cell death. Moreover, this NH offers fluorescence tracking features without therapy due to the specific excitation of NI in the green and emission in the orange. This strategy opens up new alternatives for successful and non-invasive antitumoral theragnosis.

INTRODUCTION

Photodynamic therapy (PDT) is a non-invasive treatment for many diseases including cancers. It is based on the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), mainly singlet oxygen (¹O₂), after selective excitation of a photosensitizer (PS) in the presence of ³O₂ and causes selective cell death.¹⁻²

Porphyrin-based PSs for PDT possess unique advantages due to their ability to be retained in tumors and to produce cytotoxic ¹O₂ upon exposure to an appropriate wavelength of light which coincidentally fits within a “therapeutic window” where tissues exhibit the best light penetration.³ Photofrin, the only Food and Drug Administration-approved drug for this therapy, suffers from certain disadvantages: its complex chemical nature; retention in skin (leading to protracted cutaneous photosensitivity); and less than optimal photophysical properties.⁴ To overcome these problems, a set of second generation PSs like

Levulans[®], Radachlorins[®], Visudyne[®] and Foscan[®] was developed.³ Chlorin-type PSs (such as bacteriochlorins) are drugs with more favorable photophysical properties (e.g., longer wavelength absorptions and greater molar absorption coefficients and shorter retention times in the skin). One such drug is Photoclor tested in a number of dose-ranging studies in cancer patients.

In addition to therapy, non-invasive in nature, fluorescence (FL) imaging instruments are simple and not expensive to operate and can allow precise assessment of the location and size of a tumor, providing information on its invasiveness in adjacent tissue.⁵⁻⁶ The potential clinical advantages of the FL technique include high signal sensitivity, especially if point measurements are used, the suitability of examining tissue surfaces (compared to the “volume” imaging of most radiological techniques), flexibility in the anatomical sites that can be interpreted with small diameter

optical fiber probes, reduction in the use of random tissue biopsies, and ease of use by clinicians.⁷

Photofrins and most of the tumor-avid long-wavelength PS (e.g. bacteriochlorins) exhibit very slight wavelength differences between their NIR absorption and emission bands (Stokes shifts). Such inherent property limits application of these molecules for FL imaging. To overcome this difficulty, Pandey *et al.* conjugated the tumour-avid Photochlor to a cyanine dye with absorption in the blue and emission in the green. The resulting bifunctional agent showed both PDT efficacy and tumour-imaging capabilities,⁸ but one of the problems in the bifunctional agent was the resonance energy transfer (RET) from the fluorophore to the PS.⁹

UCNPs can be designed to incorporate both diagnosis and therapy by using the synergic effects between UCNPs and a PS.¹⁰ UCNPs are interesting nanofluorophores that exhibit narrow emission bands after NIR excitation, which penetrates deeply into tissues.¹¹ UCNPs are also appropriate medical imaging systems that can be used not only for diagnosis of a disease and visualization of NP accumulation but also to facilitate the evaluation of treatment outcomes.^{10, 12-15} In addition, two-photon (TP) fluorescent molecules play key roles in TP-imaging among which naphthalimide has been used more often because of its unique photophysical properties.¹⁶ Moreover, those with electron-donor groups can present TP absorption cross-section >100 GM.¹⁷

Figure 1. A) Schematic representation of the components required for a NIR-responsive NH with NIR-theragnosis and FL tracking without therapy capacity. B) Structure and optical features of the components used for building the NH consisting of *N*-aminobacterio-purpurinimide (PP), 1,8-naphthalimide (NI), and UCNP (NaYF₄: Yb, Er, Tm).

To prepare nanoparticles (NPs) enabling NIR-theragnosis where both NIR-to-NIR imaging and NIR-PDT therapeutic capabilities are integrated while offering imaging tracking capabilities without inducing therapy is challenging (Figure 1). To this purpose, we

devised the suitability of a nanohybrid (NH) consisting of i) a bacteriochlorin derivative, namely a *N*-amino-bacterio-purpurinimide (PP), which exhibited broadband absorption in the whole UV-to-NIR range but from 580 to 675 nm;¹⁸⁻²⁰ ii) an orange emitting 1,8-naphthalimide (NI), with an electron-donor group and as a consequence with broadband in the visible (absorption spectrum extending up to around 560 nm),²¹ and orange FL; and iii) a NIR-responsive tri-doped NP, NaYF₄: Yb, Er, Tm (UC_{YbErTm}) exhibiting narrow emissions at 475, 520, 540, 650 and 808 nm appeared suitable taking into account the optical properties of NI and PP (Figure 1B).

The overlap between the UC_{YbErTm} emission and PP absorption (up to ca. 820 nm) would make efficient ¹O₂ generation possible. The excitation of NI at green wavelengths where PP is almost transparent, would lead to an orange FL ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 620$ nm), thus providing an independent emissive channel for FL tracking without applying PDT.

We report here that UC_{YbErTm}@PP/NI presents an effective PS (PP) and an orange tracker (NI), which acts as an independent emissive channel for FL tracking without applying PDT, i.e. innocuous when monitoring the emission. In addition, these NHs are suitable for NIR-theragnosis, offering simultaneous NIR-therapy and NIR-to-NIR tracking. The production of cytotoxic ¹O₂ is maximized under NIR excitation due to the co-localization of UC, PP and NI, which not only facilitates the effective RET from UC to PP, but it also provides effective ET to NI subsequently followed by ET to PP, i.e. NI also acts as PS enhancer as it will be shown along the manuscript. In vitro assays demonstrate that UC_{YbErTm}@PP/NI is non-cytotoxic but extremely effective for NIR-induced cancer cell death.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

UC_{YbErTm}@PP/NI was prepared from ligand-free NaYF₄: Yb, Er, Tm UCNPs (UC_{YbErTm}, see details in ESI and Figure S1), which were capped first with NI and then with PP to minimize the aggregation of PP on the UCNP surface (for PP and NI synthesis and optical features see details in ESI, Scheme S1, and Figures S2-S3). NI was directly anchored to the UC_{YbErTm} surface via its carboxylic group; the absorption spectrum corroborated the successful formation of UC_{YbErTm}@NI (Figure S4). The FL spectrum of UC_{YbErTm}@NI registered at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 365$ nm (Figure S4) showed two emission bands (λ_{max} at 445 and 637 nm), due to the fact that NI is a dual-emissive 1,8-naphthalimide (see discussion in ESI). Emission spectra of UC_{YbErTm}@NI at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 975$ nm showed a strong quenching (~80%) of the UCNP green emission, this is consistent with RET from Er⁺³ to NI,²² see Figure S5.

The successful anchoring of PP to the UC_{YbErTm}@NI surface was consistent with the acidity of its hydrazide group. Direct grafting of PP to the NP surface should enable efficient RET and also stop leaching of PP.^{10-11, 22-}

²⁴ The formation of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni was corroborated by different techniques, such as absorption and emission (λ_{exc} 975 and 490 nm) spectroscopy (Figure 2); see ESI and Figure S6 for further data. The loading of the PS in UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni has been estimated as 16 PP and 9 NI per NP.

The UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni emission ($\lambda_{exc}=975$ nm) below 600 nm decreased (by about 40%) and so did that at 800 nm, concomitantly with the appearance of a strong band at about 830 nm (Figure 2B).

Figure 2. A) UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni absorption spectrum (- -) and emission spectrum $\lambda_{exc}=490$ nm (-). B) Emission ($\lambda_{exc}=975$ nm) spectra normalized at 650 nm of 1 mg/mL dispersions of UC_{YbErTm} (- -) and UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni (-). All spectra were registered in acetonitrile.

Control experiments were carried out in order to elucidate the origin of this relatively strong emission. To this aim, an UC_{YbErTm}@PP/PEG NH and an UC_{YbEr}@PP analog were prepared from UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni and UC_{YbEr}, respectively (see details in ESI), which demonstrates the higher affinity of the hydrazide group than the carboxylate group for the UC surface. After NIR irradiation, both UC_{YbErTm}@PP/PEG and UC_{YbEr}@PP showed a considerable quenching of the UCNP emission below 600 nm as compared with that of the corresponding UC (Figures S7 and S8), but the NIR-induced PP emission at 830 nm was low, thus evidencing the important role of NI in the drastic enhancement of PP NIR emission in UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni (Figure 2B). Consequently, the strong emission band at about 830 nm after NIR excitation of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni can mainly be attributed to efficient ET from NI to PP due to the overlap between the greenish-blue emission of NI and the absorption spectrum of PP (see also Figure S9).

Interestingly, comparison between the absorption spectra of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni, PP and UC_{YbErTm}@NI (Figures 2A, S3, S4) evidenced that the absorbance in the 450-500 nm range is mostly due to the NI. Figure 2A shows the emission band centered at 630 nm (orange FL) after excitation of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni at 490 nm; therefore, UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni allows for independent tracking without applying PDT (i.e., no PS excitation).

Indeed, time-resolved measurements (Figures S10-S13 and Tables S2-S4) showed that the green emission of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/PEG exhibits a similar decay time (55.2 μ s) to that of UC_{YbErTm} (60.2 μ s). Taking into account that passivation of the NP would increase the decay time,²⁵ those similar values were consistent with ET from the lanthanide donors in the UCNP located in the range of effective distances to PP anchored at the surface (R_0 ca. 3-4 nm).²² In addition, the decay lifetime of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni shortened by a half (28.5 μ s). The faster decay of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni emission than that of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/PEG was consistent with the greater amount of PP in this NH together with the presence of NI.

Moreover, prolonged irradiation of PP and NI (at 490 and 975 nm) and of PP in UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni and UC_{YbErTm}@PP/PEG (975 nm) proved their remarkable photostability (Figures S14-S16). Indeed, the optical properties of the NHs remained identical after 48h in a typical culture medium (Figure S17).

The effectiveness of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni and UC_{YbErTm}@PP/PEG in 1O_2 generation after NIR excitation was confirmed by means of a specific probe, 9,10-anthracenediyl-bis(methylene)dimalonic acid (ABDA). Figure S18 compares the decrease of ABDA FL over time upon NIR irradiation of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni (at 975 nm) and PP (at both 975 nm and 365 nm) and shows the relevance of the cooperative action between the NH components (UCNP, PP, and NI) for the efficient and effective production of the toxic species under NIR light.

Then, the toxicity of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni and UC_{YbErTm}@PP/PEG were checked in vitro by incubating different concentrations of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni and UC_{YbErTm}@PP/PEG for 24 h in the culture medium of SH-SY5Y cells, a cell line derived from human neuroblastoma. Cell viability (XTT assay) revealed that UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni and UC_{YbErTm}@PP/PEG were no cytotoxic even at high concentrations (500 μ g·mL⁻¹, Figure S19).

Next, the uptake by cells incubating with 100 μ g·mL⁻¹ of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni in the culture medium for 4 h was determined (see Figure S20 and a hypothesis for the internalisation in ESI).

Fluorescence imaging upon excitation at 975 nm showed the emission of UC in the 515-580 nm range (Figure 3A) and the emission of NI in 590-650 nm (Figure 3B); so, the overlap of the two emissive channels (Figure 3C) showed the co-localization of UCNP and

NI inside the cell, which confirmed the internalization of the NH (see control analysis in Figure S21).

NI role as an independent imaging agent would allow for cell visualization without performing PDT. Direct excitation of NI at 488 nm resulted in an intense cytoplasmic cell labelling in the 570-670 nm range (Figure 3D). Thus, the ability of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/NI to visualize cells without performing PDT was corroborated.

Figure 3. A-C) Confocal microscope images of cells incubated with UC_{YbErTm}@PP/NI; A) $\lambda_{ex}=975$ nm, $\lambda_{em}=515-580$ nm; B) $\lambda_{ex}=975$ nm, $\lambda_{em}=590-650$ nm; C) overlap of A and B (yellow); D) $\lambda_{ex}=488$ nm, $\lambda_{em}=570-670$ nm. Scale bar: 50 μ m.

In addition, confocal microscopy experiments were also carried out to corroborate that cells incubated with NI can be excited at NIR wavelengths where UCNP does not absorb. As expected, excitation at 880 nm enabled the emission of NI (Figure S22).

SH-SY5Y cells were incubated with 100 μ g·mL⁻¹ of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/NI or vehicle (culture medium) for 4 h and samples were irradiated up to 7 min at 975 nm (density power of 20.75 mW·cm⁻²; doses up to 8.7 J·cm⁻²). Cell viability was evaluated using Life Technologies LIVE/DEAD® Kit. Only cells with disrupted membranes exhibited red-FL from the live-cell impermeable nucleic acid stain ethidium homodimer-1 (EthD1; $\lambda_{ex}=510-560$ nm; $\lambda_{em}=590$ nm), see Figure 4a. No perceptible changes were detected in control cells after 7 min of irradiation (control 7 min) and without light excitation ($t=0$ min). NIR-irradiated areas containing UC@PP/NI presented high numbers of dead cells (see Figure 4b, Table S5). Our NH has shown an astonishing performance at low light dose (see Table S1 for comparison between UC_{YbErTm}@PP/NI and reported relevant UCNP-based PDT agents).

Figure 4. A) Cell viability was evaluated using Cell LIVE/DEAD® Kit (damaged cells: red and intact cells: green); (a) Control SH-SY5Y cells irradiated at 975 nm for 7 min. (b-f) SH-SY5Y cells treated with UC_{YbErTm}@PP/NI without light irradiation (b) and irradiated for up to 7 min (c-f). B) Cell death quantification shows that irradiation at 975 nm for 3, 5 or 7 min results in a dramatic decrease in cell survival. Data shown as mean \pm SEM ($n=3-4$), *** $p<0.001$. C) Toluidine blue stained semithin sections (a-f) incubated with UC_{YbErTm}@PP/NI and UC_{YbErTm}@PP/PEG and without UCNPs after NIR irradiation and without irradiation. Electron microscopy images of irradiated cells (g-i). Scale bars: A = 200 μ m; C (a-f) = 10 μ m; C (g-i) = 5 μ m.

Importantly, toluidine blue stained semithin sections (Figure 4c) showed that, upon irradiation, the NH-treated cells were highly vacuolated and contained large dense cytoplasmic aggregations, especially in the case of those treated with UC_{YbErTm}@PP/NI, whereas non-irradiated cells

presented a healthy appearance. No changes were observed in irradiated vehicle-treated cells (Figures 4c(C-F)).

Further study of NH-treated cells by TEM revealed that, once irradiated, these cells contained large proteinaceous vacuoles and dense bodies, indicating material degradation (Figures 4c (G-I)). Moreover, phagocytic vacuoles accumulating swelled mitochondria, dilated endoplasmic reticulum cisternae, and even nuclear fragments were frequently observed in these cells, mainly in the case of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni. These results suggest that NIR irradiation of cells incorporating the NHs can produce ROS and, as a consequence, the cells present typical signs of oxidative stress.

CONCLUSION

We report here a novel nanohybrid useful for NIR-induced PDT that bears an independent fluorescent reporting molecule. UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni was not cytotoxic and proved to be extremely active for NIR-inducing cancer cell death. The cells present typical signs of oxidative stress due to NIR-induced generation of ROS. The NH can be tracked down by following the orange Ni FL after selective excitation at greenish-blue wavelengths and at NIR wavelengths where the UCNP does not absorb, thus allowing the tracking of the NH without applying PDT. This strategy opens up new alternatives of nanohybrid design for successful and non-invasive antitumoral theragnosis. In addition, the use of neodymium-doped UCNP nanohybrids will offer deeper light penetration and these nanohybrids are worth studying.

METHODS AND EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Materials. Chemicals used for the UCNPs synthesis were lanthanide chlorides (YCl₃·6H₂O, YbCl₃·6H₂O, ErCl₃·6H₂O and TmCl₃·6H₂O (>99.9%, all of them)), 1-octadecene (95%), oleic acid (70%), NaOH and NH₄F (99.99%). All these chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used as received without previous purification. Chemicals used for the synthesis of PP and Ni were purchased from commercial sources and were of the highest grade. Solvents were purified and dried according to standard procedures

Synthesis of UC_{YbErTm}@Ni. In a 15 mL centrifuge tube, 10 mg of UC_{YbErTm}, 2.3 mg of Ni and 1 mL ethanol were sonicated for 15 minutes until complete dispersion. Then, 5 mL of triethanolamine solution in water (TEA, pH = 8) were added and the reaction was stirred in an orbital shaker at 400 rpm for 24 h in the darkness. The nanoparticles were recovered by centrifugation (9000 rpm, 15 min, 25 °C) and washed with acetonitrile (7 mL, 6 times) followed by centrifugation. An orange precipitate was obtained and dried under vacuum for 24 h in the dark. Finally, the dried precipitate was re-dispersed in 1 mL of ethanol.

Taking into account the molar extinction coefficient of Ni in acetonitrile ($\epsilon_{479} = 15346 \text{ M}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$), we

estimated an amount of 0.18 mg of Ni (0.34 mmol) per 1 mg of UCNPs in the UC_{YbErTm}@Ni nanohybrid.

Synthesis of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni. To 1 mL of the ethanol dispersion of UC_{YbErTm}@Ni previously obtained, 3.1 mg of PP were added and sonicated for 10 minutes. After that, 5 mL of a solution of TEA solution (pH = 8) were added. The reaction mixture was stirred in an orbital shaker for 24 h at 400 rpm in the dark. Finally, nanoparticles were separated by centrifugation (9000 rpm, 15 min, 25 °C). The brown precipitate was washed 7 times with 6 mL of acetonitrile followed by centrifugation. The nanohybrid 1 obtained was dried at vacuum for 24 h in the dark.

Taking into account the TGA analysis and the absorption spectra of the supernatants an amount of 0.2 mg of PP (0.33 mmol) and 0.1 mg of Ni (0.19 mmol) per 1 mg of nanohybrid was estimated.

Synthesis of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/PEG. 5 mg of UC_{YbErTm}@PP/Ni were dispersed in 5 mL of degassed CHCl₃. To this mixture, 30 mg of SH-PEG-NH₂ were added and stirred at 60 °C in an oil bath for 24 hours. After solvent evaporation with nitrogen flow, the solid obtained was re-dispersed in 3 mL of acetonitrile by sonication for 10 minutes. Then, nanoparticles were recovered by centrifugation at 9000 rpm for 15 minutes. The precipitate was washed four times with 3 mL of acetonitrile followed by centrifugation at 9000 rpm, 15 min. The resultant precipitate was dispersed in 1 mL of milliQ water. Taking into account the TGA analysis and the absorption spectra of the supernatants, an amount of 0.11 mg of PP (0.18 mmol) and 0.01 mg of PEG (3.3 nmol) per 1 mg of UC in UC_{YbErTm}@PP/PEG was estimated. The loading in the of photosensitizer per nanohybrid has been estimated as 8 PP per nanoparticle.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information: experimental details, HRTEM images, TGA, photophysical characterization, fitted kinetics, photostability studies, singlet oxygen generation, internalization of UCNPs, additional confocal images. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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Author Contributions

O.A.F. and J.P.P. designed the nano hybrid; J.P.P. wrote the manuscript; L.F.S. performed the synthesis of the nano hybrids and the physical and photophysical measurements under the supervision of M.G.B.; L.F.S. and M.G.B. participated in data analyses and commented on the manuscript; P.A.P. did the theoretical work to find the structure of NI appropriate for combining with PP; M.A.Z. synthesized NI under the supervision of P.A.P.; V.H-P. and J.M.G-V carried out the studies in cells; D.A.P., M.A.G. and A.F.M. extracted the bacteriopurpurinimide from biomass and then carried out the modification to give rise to PP. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Notes

There are no conflicts to declare.

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ABBREVIATIONS

ABDA, 9,10-anthracenediyl-bis(methylene)dimalonic acid; ET, energy transfer; FL, fluorescence; NI, 1,8-naphthalimide; NIR, near-infrared; $^1\text{O}_2$, singlet oxygen; PDT, photodynamic therapy; PP, N-aminobacterio-purpurinimide; PS, photosensitizer; RET, resonance energy transfer; ROS, reactive oxygen species; UCNP, upconversion nanoparticles; UV, ultraviolet; $\text{UC}_{\text{YbErTm}}$, $\text{NaYF}_4\text{:Yb,Er,Tm}$; VIS, visible.

REFERENCES

- (1) Brown, S. B.; Brown, E. A.; Walker, I., The present and future role of photodynamic therapy in cancer treatment. *Lancet Oncol.* **2004**, *5* (8), 497-508.
- (2) Dougherty, T. J., Photodynamic Therapy. *Photochem. Photobiol.* **1993**, *58* (6), 895-900.
- (3) Ethirajan, M.; Chen, Y.; Joshi, P.; Pandey, R. K., The role of porphyrin chemistry in tumor imaging and photodynamic therapy. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2011**, *40* (1), 340-362.
- (4) Dougherty, T. J., An Update on Photodynamic Therapy Applications. *J. Clin. Laser Med. Surg.* **2002**, *20* (1), 3-7.
- (5) Pandey, R. K.; James, N.; Chen, Y.; Dobhal, M. P., Cyanine Dye-Based Compounds for Tumor Imaging With and Without Photodynamic Therapy. In *Heterocyclic Polymethine Dyes: Synthesis, Properties and Applications*, Streckowski, L., Ed. Springer Berlin Heidelberg: Berlin, Heidelberg, 2008; pp 41-74.
- (6) Jäger, H. R.; Taylor, M. N.; Theodossy, T.; Hopper, C., MR Imaging-Guided Interstitial Photodynamic Laser Therapy for Advanced Head and Neck Tumors. *Am. J. Neuroradiol.* **2005**, *26* (5), 1193-1200.
- (7) Frangioni, J. V., In vivo near-infrared fluorescence imaging. *Curr. Opin. Chem. Biol.* **2003**, *7* (5), 626-634.
- (8) Williams, M. P. A.; Ethirajan, M.; Ohkubo, K.; Chen, P.; Pera, P.; Morgan, J.; White, W. H.; Shibata, M.; Fukuzumi, S.; Kadish, K. M.; Pandey, R. K., Synthesis, Photophysical, Electrochemical, Tumor-Imaging, and Phototherapeutic Properties of Purpurinimide-N-substituted Cyanine Dyes Joined with Variable Lengths of Linkers. *Bioconjugate Chem.* **2011**, *22* (11), 2283-2295.
- (9) Panchenko, P. A.; Sergeeva, A. N.; Fedorova, O. A.; Fedorov, Y. V.; Reshetnikov, R. I.; Schelkunova, A. E.; Grin, M. A.; Mironov, A. F.; Jonusauskas, G., Spectroscopical study of

bacteriopurpurinimide-naphthalimide conjugates for fluorescent diagnostics and photodynamic therapy. *J. Photochem. Photobiol. B* **2014**, *133*, 140-144.

- (10) Liu, X.; Que, I.; Kong, X.; Zhang, Y.; Tu, L.; Chang, Y.; Wang, T. T.; Chan, A.; Lowik, C. W. G. M.; Zhang, H., In vivo 808 nm image-guided photodynamic therapy based on an upconversion theranostic nanoplatform. *Nanoscale* **2015**, *7* (36), 14914-14923.

- (11) Francés-Soriano, L.; González-Béjar, M.; Pérez-Prieto, J., Synergistic Effects in Organic-Coated Upconversion Nanoparticles. In *Upconverting Nanomaterials: Perspectives, Synthesis, and Applications*, Altavilla, C., Ed. CRC Press Boca Raton, Florida (USA), 2016; pp 101-138.

- (12) González-Béjar, M.; Francés-Soriano, L.; Pérez-Prieto, J., Upconversion Nanoparticles for Bioimaging and Regenerative Medicine. *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* **2016**, *4*, 47.

- (13) Dong, H.; Du, S. R.; Zheng, X. Y.; Lyu, G. M.; Sun, L. D.; Li, L. D.; Zhang, P. Z.; Zhang, C.; Yan, C. H., Lanthanide Nanoparticles: From Design toward Bioimaging and Therapy. *Chem. Rev.* **2015**, *115* (19), 10725-10815.

- (14) DaCosta, M. V.; Doughan, S.; Han, Y.; Krull, U. J., Lanthanide upconversion nanoparticles and applications in bioassays and bioimaging: A review. *Anal. Chim. Acta* **2014**, *832*, 1-33.

- (15) Rieffel, J.; Chen, F.; Kim, J.; Chen, G.; Shao, W.; Shao, S.; Chitgupi, U.; Hernandez, R.; Graves, S. A.; Nickles, R. J.; Prasad, P. N.; Kim, C.; Cai, W.; Lovell, J. F., Hexamodal imaging with porphyrin-phospholipid-coated upconversion nanoparticles. *Adv. Mater.* **2015**, *27* (10), 1785-1790.

- (16) Zhu, X.; Li, Y.; Zan, W.; Zhang, J.; Chen, Z.; Liu, X.; Qi, F.; Yao, X.; Zhang, X.; Zhang, H., A two-photon off-on fluorescence probe for imaging thiols in live cells and tissues. *Photochem. Photobiol. Sci.* **2016**, *15* (3), 412-419.

- (17) Li, J.; Meng, F.; Tian, H.; Mi, J.; Ji, W., Highly Fluorescent Naphthalimide Derivatives for Two-photon Absorption Materials. *Chem. Lett.* **2005**, *34* (7), 922-923.

- (18) Mironov, A. F.; Grin, M. A.; Tsiprovskiy, A. G.; Dzardanov, D. V.; Golovin, K. V.; Feofanov, A. V.; Yakubovskaya, R. I. Bacteriochlorophyll a-based hydrazides possessing photodynamic activity and method for their preparation. Patent RF 2223274 (in Russian), 10.02.2014, 2004.

- (19) Pantiushenko, I. V.; Rudakovskaya, P. G.; Starovoytova, A. V.; Mikhaylovskaya, A. A.; Abakumov, M. A.; Kaplan, M. A.; Tsygankov, A. A.; Majouga, A. G.; Grin, M. A.; Mironov, A. F., Development of bacteriochlorophyll a-based near-infrared photosensitizers conjugated to gold nanoparticles for photodynamic therapy of cancer. *Biochemistry (Moscow)* **2015**, *80* (6), 752-762.

- (20) Mironov, A. F.; Grin, M. A.; Tsiprovskiy, A. G.; Kachala, V. V.; Karmakova, T. A.; Plyutinskaya, A. D.; Yakubovskaya, R. I., New bacteriochlorin derivatives with a fused N-aminoimide ring. *J. Porphyrins Phthalocyanines* **2003**, *07* (11), 725-730.

- (21) Sergeeva, A. N.; Panchenko, P. A.; Fedorov, Y. V.; Fedorova, O. A., Synthesis and sensor properties of crown-containing derivatives of 4-(1,5-diphenyl- Δ^2 -pyrazolin-3-yl)-1,8-naphthalimide. *Prot. Met. Phys. Chem. Surf* **2012**, *48* (5), 524-533.

- (22) Muhr, V.; Würth, C.; Kraft, M.; Buchner, M.; Baeumner, A. J.; Resch-Genger, U.; Hirsch, T., Particle-Size-Dependent Förster Resonance Energy Transfer from Upconversion Nanoparticles to Organic Dyes. *Anal. Chem.* **2017**, *89* (9), 4868-4874.

- (23) González-Béjar, M.; Liras, M.; Francés-Soriano, L.; Voliani, V.; Herranz-Pérez, V.; Duran-Moreno, M.; Garcia-Verdugo, J. M.; Alarcon, E. I.; Scaiano, J. C.; Pérez-Prieto, J., NIR excitation of upconversion nano hybrids containing a surface grafted Bodipy induces oxygen-mediated cancer cell death. *J. Mater. Chem. B* **2014**, *2* (28), 4554-4563.

(24) Wang, M.; Chen, Z.; Zheng, W.; Zhu, H.; Lu, S.; Ma, E.; Tu, D.; Zhou, S.; Huang, M.; Chen, X., Lanthanide-doped upconversion nanoparticles electrostatically coupled with photosensitizers for near-infrared-triggered photodynamic therapy. *Nanoscale* **2014**, *6* (14), 8274-8282.

(25) Schindelin, J.; Arganda-Carreras, I.; Frise, E.; Kaynig, V.; Longair, M.; Pietzsch, T.; Preibisch, S.; Rueden, C.; Saalfeld, S.; Schmid, B.; Tinevez, J.-Y.; White, D. J.; Hartenstein, V.; Eliceiri, K.;

Tomancak, P.; Cardona, A., Fiji: an open-source platform for biological-image analysis. *Nat. Meth.* **2012**, *9* (7), 676-682.

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